

SCIENTIFIC ANALYSIS OF SROTAS AND SROTODUSHTI

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INTRODUCTION

Kha vaigunya and srotodushti are a crucial and necessary phase in the illness's manifestation process. Among these two the srotodushti is very frequently recognized and management is intended consequently. Regarding the concept of Kha vaigunya, this is recognition, its contributory factors, its significance While therapy and its consequence in disease manifestation is often ignored.

Sroto dushti

Srotodushti causes genesis of a disease and their normalcy brings the health [1]. Sroto dushti is caused by the ahara (diet) and vihara (activities) which aggravates the doshas and which are unlike dhatus in their qualities. [2]

Though the definition of srotodushti is not directly referenced found anywhere in samhitas but the word exclusively described in Charaka samhita while explaining the etiological factors which brings abnormality in srotas. According to Charaka there are 13 types of abhyantara srotas (internal structures) and their specific causative factors for each are described [3], [4].

The symptoms of each sroto dushti are presented but There is no mention of rasadi sapta sroto dushti lakshanas individually. However, the acharya made a suggestion that these are merely the dhatu pradoshaja vikaras. Only because these arise from dhatuvaha sroto duhstis [5].

SROTODUSTI LAKSHANAS

Four symptoms and signs of srotodusti takes place namely, Sanga (obstruction), Siragranthi (aneurysm), Atipravritti (increasing activity), and Vimargagamana (opposite direction). These four kinds could happen. either independently or in combination. Among four, sanga gives rise to the majority of the diseases. [6].

Because of the strong relationship that typically exists between the dhatus and their corresponding srotas, the pradasha or dushti in the srotas may leads to dushti in the dhatus and vice versa [7].

2. Kha vaigunya –

The term vaigunya kha is a **vividly found** in classical texts of ayurveda. Vyana vata impel the ahara rasa (final product of digestion) through hridaya (Heart) to whole body. While circulating the driven rasa lodgings in the region of susceptibility i.e.kha vaigunya leading to development of diseases [8].

Sushruta mentioned that kupita (aggravated) doshas circulate all over the body and produce diseases when they come across the seat of susceptibility (kha vaigunya). [9].

The word kha vaigunya is described as sroto vaigunya in commentary of Chakrapani [8] and Dalhana [9] while Arunadautta expressed kha vaigunya as sroto duhsti [10].

DISCUSSION

KHA VAIGUNYA- Kha refers to Srotas and Vaigunya to Vigunata which are both detailed below.

Srotas:

“As per Sravanaat Srotamsi [11]. The entities responsible for sravana, or secretion, are referred to as srotas.

Vaigunya (Vigunata) :

Any a departure from its usual karma (functions) and guna (characteristic properties) is known as vigunata. Hence vigunata (abnormality) of srotas may be broadly classified as **karmataha vaigunya and gunataha vaigunya**

1. Karmataha vaigunya

It is caused by the Guna vaigunya of the **Srotas, Dhatwagni mandya or vriddhi, Influence of purva and para dhatu and ama.**

a. Guna vaigunya of srotas:

When it comes to genetic beeja dushti, the srotas become both physiologically and operationally abnormal and as a result it cannot carry out its normal functions.

b. Dhatwagni mandya or vriddhi

Regarding Dhatwagni abnormality the transformation within the srotas is insufficient, resulting in sama dhatu or dhatu vriddhi similar to apakwa dhatu utpatti as result abnormality inside the srotas occurs, leading to karma vigunata [12].

c. Influence of purva (previous dhatu) and para dhatu (subsequent dhatu): If purva dhatu (previous dhatu) is sama (incorrectly converted), the purva dhatu will likewise affect the para dhatu, making the uttara dhatu (subsequent dhatu) sama. (13).

For example–sama rasa – resulting in utpatti of sama rakta dhatu and so on. Due to improper poshaka amsha (ahara rasa/essential nutrients), the srotas (channels) and karma (functions) of uttara dhatu (subsequent dhatu)also becomes abnormal. Just like, the leakage from gutter pipe/sewage pipe when released into the water supply pipe pollutes the whole drinking water.

d. Ama : development of ama either by jatharagnimandyaor dhatwagni mandyais the main culprit to cause the obstruction inside the srotas[14]. Normal Srotas is a hollow structure and it may be sthulau (macro channels) or sukshma mukhi (micro channels).The paths of circulation transmit the dhatus, or tissue elements or their components, changing as they travel to their final location. As shown by the word "Parinamapadyamanam," the

channels convey tissue constituents that are changing from their preceding states, such as rakta (blood), to their ensuing states, such as rasa (plasma, WBC, lymph, etc.). Ayanarthena signify that only those movable dhatus that are meant to be changed into another dhatu that is located elsewhere are carried by the channels of circulation; they do not carry the sthira (stable) dhatus. Hollowness (soushirya) is the characteristic property of srotas [15] due to presence of ama the normal characteristic property of srotas will no longer be present leading to malformation as a result karma vaigunya (abnormal functions) occurs. Ultimately vahana (transportation) of parinama mapadhyamana dhatu (ultimate end product of digestion) will be interrupted. [15] [16].

2. Guna vaigunya (anatomical and physiological defects)

Prakruta GUNA of srotas (Structure)

Similar to those in the lotus stalk, the srotas have tiny, wide, long, and far openings through which rasa "nourishes" the body. The srotas would be cylindrical, 'either sthula (large, macroscopic) or anu (atomic or microscopic), dirgha (long) or prathana (reticulated), and their color and form would match the dhatu they carried.) [17]. Any divergence One of the qualities mentioned above is the guna vaigunya of srotas. (change in the structure of the srotas).

Guna vaigunya (anatomical and physiological defects) can occur by following causes-

a. Beeja dushti (Genetic defect):

The characteristic structural property of the srotas is predetermined by the excellence of the genes and defective gene may induce anomalies in the srotas' anatomy and physiology, which can result in development of abnormalities in the body.

a. Defective formation of dhatu

Defective formation of dhatus by any means leads to vitiation inside the srotas.

SROTO DUSHTI

Srotodushti means to vitiation of srotas leading to many abnormalities in the srotas and it is due to abnormal doshas and dushyas. [18].

Once the dosha dushyasammurchana happens in the srotas, it causes srotodushti resulting in development of dhatu pradoshaja vikara, Indriya pradoshaja vikaras etc. [19].

Circulating doshas and dushyas that deposit in srotas due to kha vaigunya mentioned as stage of sthanaasamshraya, at this stage there is interaction between the doshas and dushyas causing the manifestation of vyadhi (disease). The stage of interaction between dosha and dushya and its consequent reactions might be considered as the srotodushti. The phase of kha vaigunya and srotodushti are taking place in the sthanasamshraya stage.

Is Srotodushti same as srotovaigunya?

The both words Kha vaigunya (sroto vaigunya) and sroto dushti are similar. Some people are of opinion that Kha vaigunya (sroto vaigunya) may perhaps be considered as precursor to the sroto dushti. Some says that Srotovaigunya is only a functional condition rather than an illness variation that is less severe. may predispose for disease manifestation. Whereas

dushtiin the A severe variation of sroto vaigunya, srotas will certainly bring about a sickness. If Sroto Dushti and Kha Vaigunya are identical, i.e. if it is believed that there is abnormality in both situations to certain extent gradually, followed by dushti in srotas should give rise to appearance of symptoms and signs i.e. sroto dushti janya lakshanas or pradoshaja vikara. It is not essential that a disease has to be present, wherever there is kha vaigunya (if it is thought to be milder degree of srotodushti). On the contrary the srotodushti surely cause the manifestation of disease (Table 1).

Table 1: Difference between **Kha Vaigunya (srotovaigunya) & Srotodushti**

S.no	Kha Vaigunya (srotovaigunya)	Srotodushti
1	Manifest before dosha dushya sammurchana	Manifest after dosha dushya sammurchana
2	It is necessary for Sthanasamshrayavastha of Kriyakala	It is necessary for Vyaktavastha of Kriyakala
3	It may manifest by minor etiological factors	It may manifest by complex etiological factors
4	This state is inference state –anuman ganya	This state is direct observation –Pratyaksha ganya
5	Purvarupa (premonitory signs and symptoms) observed in this state	Rupa (signs and symptoms of the disease) observed in this state
6	Dosha sanchaya, prakopa, and prasara lakshanas observed	Four symptoms and signs of srotodushti are observed viz. Atipravritti (increased activity), Sanga (obstruction), Siragranthi (aneurysm/haemorrhoids/varicose veins),and Vimargagamana (opposite direction)

The word Kha vaigunya is used while elucidating the course of development of disease. The circulating Doshas become stuck in a vulnerable area i.e. Kha vaigunya, which can be brought on by genetic defect and other environmental factors and so on. After having stuck there, they remain stay there until they get appropriate time for the manifestation of a vyadhi (disease). If the person continuously indulges the etiological factors which brings vitiation in srotas leading to vaigunya in the srotas and produce pradoshaja vikara or vyadhi. Due to vaigunya if milder form of srotodushti develops it may not cause any lakshana or disease because lack of prominent interactions between dosha and dushya. Prominent interactions between dosha and dushya provide the favourable environment to cause a disease.

It is mentioned in the texts that once there is a dushti (dosha dushti) in dhatu and srotas leading to development of symptoms and signs of that particular disease. Such opinion has been observed in vividhashita pitiya chapter, dosha Dhatu dhatuvaha srotas dushti – resulting in pradoshaja vikara [20]. This is true in case of pradoshaja vikara i.e. the role of dosha dushti is primary in causing the damage to dhatus and srotas. At this juncture dhatus might be normal but The function of dosha dushti in srotas and dhatu is playing important role in diseases manifestation. Therefore some scholars says that srotodushti and kha vaigunya are not identical, but are intimately connected.

Primary and secondary kha vaigunya are the two important causative factors to cause sroto vaigunya. Beeja dushti janya kha vaigunya was created as a result of the effect of defective genes. The secondary kha vaigunya results due to deeds done by individuals after birth in addition to genetic one.

EXAMPLES FROM THE CONTEMPORARY SCIENCE REGARDING KHA VAIGUNYA AND SROTODUSHTI –

Contemporary classics have described about a number of conditions which replenish the concept of khavignya, srotodushti and disease development. This section will detail those concepts.

A. Metaplastic and dysplastic changes – Metaplasia is a reversible kind of change brought about by abnormal stimuli in the adult epithelial or mesenchymal cells. They may either revert back to normal on removal of the stimulus or may progress further to dysplasia and cancer. **Squamous epithelial metaplasia** occurs when the specialised cells present in a region of the body are not able to withstand an offending agent or stimulus and transform into a less specialised but stronger squamous epithelium as occurs in the bronchus of chronic smokers (from pseudo-stratified columnar ciliated epithelium) or uterine endocervix in prolapse and ageing (from simple columnar epithelium) or renal pelvis and urinary bladder in cases of chronic infection and stones (from transitional epithelium) or in cases of vitamin A deficiency in the bronchi, urinary tract, lacrimal, salivary gland, eyes, nose etc. **Columnar epithelial metaplasia** occurs in the intestine in cases of healed chronic gastric ulcer or in Barrets's oesophagus (from normal squamous epithelium) or in cervical erosion etc. when there is transformation to columnar epithelium.

Dysplasia is characterized by cellular proliferation and a number of cytologic changes which may precede or accompany metaplasia. Metaplasia may be reversible on the removal of the offending agent or may even progress and evolve into cancer.[21]

These examples of metaplasia and dysplasia as described above, in their initial stages, when they are clinically silent are very near to the concept of khavaigunya; however, these conditions when start presenting with clinical features depict the stages of Srotodushti and evolve further into vyadhi.

A. Increased capillary permeability– In a healthy normal tissue the fluid balance between the micro vasculature and interstitial cells is well maintained on the basis of two opposite sets of forces; first the forces causing the outward movement of fluid from the blood vessels i.e colloid osmotic pressure and intravascular hydrostatic pressure of the interstitial fluid and second the forces which cause the movement of interstitial fluid into the blood vasculature i.e. interstitial fluid hydrostatic pressure and intravascular colloid osmotic pressure. Any little amount of fluid left in the interstitial compartment is drained by the lymphatics. The balance of these three processes results in no oedema present normally. However, the balance of these three forces gets deranged in cases of inflammation. Then, the capillary endothelium properties change because of damage due to various etiological agents as toxins, drugs, chemicals, physical agents etc. and become leaky resulting in the decrease of colloid osmotic

pressure intravascularly and increased osmotic pressure of the interstitial space resulting in outward flow of fluid into the interstitial spaces resulting in oedema. [22] The change in the capillary endothelium permeability relates to the stage of khavaigunya which causes the development of gaps between the endothelial cells and consequently leads to development of oedema clinically as described above or into the clinical presentation of inflammation (in association with hemodynamic changes through the mechanism of increased vascularity, cellular events etc.) and these pathological events correlate to sroto-dushti.

B. Impaired venous drainage – The pathogenesis of passive hyperemia or congestion develops due to the development of any sort of obstruction in the venous outflow, which, on further progression causes the venous congestion in affected tissues as in liver, kidney, lungs etc. leading to the various clinical presentations.[23] The process of development of obstruction in the venous drainage relates to khavaigunya and the further steps to srotodushti which are associated with clinical presentation.

C. The development of Anaphylactic reaction - This process of development of anaphylactic reaction also clearly demonstrates the presence of the two stages of khavaigunya and srotodushti. The stage of first contact with the antigen in which sensitization of the body takes place by the circulating B lymphocytes which differentiate into the IgE secreting plasma cells and the secreted IgE antibody binds to Fc receptor of the mast cells and basophils, making them fully sensitized for the next event. Whole of this process stated above meant for priming the body for the anaphylactic reaction is like the described concept of khavaigunya which alters the inherent properties of the body and its channels predisposing them to disease development. The later stage of the second exposure of the antigen and its consequences which present with the clinical features of anaphylaxis is the state resembling srotodushti concept & the consequences include the development of enhanced vascular permeability, contraction of smooth muscle, and early vasoconstriction that is followed by vasodilation, increased secretions from the nose, stomach, and eyes, eosinophilia, neutrophilia etc. [24].

D. Genetic and Nutritional diseases - The concept of genetic and nutritional diseases [25] also relate to the concept of khavaigunya through defective formation of tissues which predisposes the individual to the development of certain kinds of diseases through the process of srotodushti. Similarly, nutritional deficiencies and disorders also cause the formation of tissues deficient in quality and thus khavaigunya which results further in srotodushti and disease.

A. Atherosclerosis - The word "atherosclerosis" comes from the Greek term " athero," referring to grease or gel (referring to the core of necrotic place where the atherosclerotic plaque is most likely to form) and "sclerosis" for stiffening or induration (corresponding to the fibrous cap of the plaque's luminal edge). The atherosclerotic plaques range in morphology from fatty streaks to advanced plaques and fibroatheromas (FAs). The signs of Atherosclerosis is characterized by arterial wall rupturing, weakening, and plaque embolization. (Aneurysm). Ischemia occurs when the vessel's flow is obstructed, either with or without embolization. Supply of blood resulting in the clinical presentation of myocardial

ischaemia (by obstruction of coronary artery), claudication or ischemia of the lower extremities (due to obstruction of iliac vessels), cerebral infarction (by obstruction of the cerebral blood supply) and others. Atherosclerotic aneurysms show a predisposition for the abdominal aorta especially, besides the other parts of aorta; the rupture of which may cause death by haemorrhage Depending on where it is, either the retroperitoneal space or the pleural cavities.[26]

Atherosclerosis in the early phase of pathogenesis is characterized by the activation of endothelial adhesion molecules and lipid retention in which the Inflammatory macrophages are important at every stage of the development of atherosclerosis. The whole process of development of the atherosclerotic plaque correlates to the concept of kha-vaigunya and the further consequences of rupture, infarct, thrombosis etc. which develop the clinical presentation as described above relate to srotodushti.

B. Thrombosis – The pathogenesis of thrombosis comprises of various events before the actual formation of thrombus. Endothelial injury is a state of khavaigunya which predisposes the vessel to the development of thrombus through the initiation of other steps as platelet activation, activation of the coagulation pathway, alteration of blood flow etc.[27] These processes together causing the development of the thrombus relate to the concept of srotodushti, which manifests with the clinical presentations in the body depending on the site of the thrombus as is described above.

CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF SROTOVAIGUNYA, SROTODUSHTI AND SROTOVIDDHA

1. Srotovaigunya plays a crucial role in the Vyadhi to occur. One Srotas can be vaigunya to the other Srotas' Dushti. This idea is comprehensible to understanding the samprapti ghatakas in Atisara. There is involvement of Annava, UdakavaSrotas and Purishava Srotas. Thus Annava, Udakava srotas acts as Srotovaigunya to cause Purishava Srotodushti
2. Even when the Srotodushti type of two people stays the same, they appear with two distinct ailments if they ingest the identical nidanas and have different Srotovaigunyas. For instance, if Person A spends all day working at a computer and strains his neck, whereas Person B works as a teacher and spends a lot of time standing in one position, then Person B's knee strain is greater. If both of them ingest any Vatakanidanas Therefore, Person B is more likely to develop Janushoola while Person A is more likely to develop Greevashoola. These two Vyadhis are not the same.
3. SrotoViddha and Srotodushti are two distinct occurrences. For instance: The Dushtilakshanas in Pranava Srotas are Atisrushta, Atibaddha, kupita, alpaalpa, Abhikshna, sashabhashoola Shwasa and the course of action to be taken is and the course of action to be taken is Shwasachikitsa. Whereas in Pranava Srotomulaviddha lakshanas **18** are the lethal Akroshana, Vinamana, Mohana, Bhramana, Vepana, and Marana. Thus, setting Dushti apart from Viddhalakshanas is very important. Shwasachikitsa shouldn't be adapted in Pranava srotoviddha manifestations.

IMPORTANCE OF KNOWLEDGE OF KHA VAIGUNYA IN CHIKITSA(TREATMENT)

It is a conventional prediction that the Kha vaigunya is an important event in disease development. The knowledge of causative factors of the srotas is important step in the management of the diseases as well as to prevent the recurrence of the disease or the appearance of a recently discovered illness. Continuous indulgence of kha vigunyakara nidanas (factors which vitiates srotas) will lead to perseverance of kha vaigunya as result person becomes more prone to develop serious diseases. Adequate knowledge about the site of kha vaigunya is important to plan the appropriate treatment. Kha vaigunya may not play any role in the initial management modalities because it primarily concentrates on correcting the dushti in that srotas, or dosha-dhatu. However, the knowledge of kha vaigunya is very necessary, While preparing the chikitsa rasayana (rejuvenative therapy) or apunarbhava chikitsa (preventive treatment modalities). Hence rasayan treatment for prevention of the disease as well as disease specific mentioned in the classical texts to correct the srotovaigunya so that disease won't manifest again. Hence while When preparing the rasayana chikitsa, it is important to focus on specific srotas. preferred, In order to prevent recurrences, it corrects the kha vaigunya by targeting it.

Conclusion

Kha vaigunya and srotodushti are a fundamental and indispensable stage in the development of disease. The srotodushti is very commonly recognized and management is anticipated accordingly. Continuous indulgence of kha vigunyakara nidanas(factors which vitiates srotas) will lead to perseverance of kha vaigunya as result person becomes more prone to develop serious diseases. Regarding the concept of kha vaigunya, its recognition, its contributory factors, its significance in treatment and its consequence in disease manifestation is often ignored as a result diseases progresses to next stage. It is a conventional prediction that the Kha vaigunya is an important event in disease development as the word kha vaigunya mentioned while explaining the genesis of disease. Some are saying that Srotovaigunya is not a disease-causing condition; rather, it is merely a functional variation that is less severe may predispose for disease manifestation. Whereas dushti in the A severe variation of sroto vaigunya, srotas will certainly cause a disease. The scientific attributes developed from the contemporary medical science also have described for several such concepts which support the above mentioned aspects related to kha vaigunya and srotodushti. Hence, on this basis the importance of kha-vaigunya and srotodushti should be appreciated along with their clinical importance and they should be addressed well in the management of diseases so as to stop their recurrence.

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